

THE PROBLEM OF PROVIDING GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FAMILY

Nargiza Rahmatova

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ANNOTATION. The article contains opinions related to ensuring gender equality today, the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan and their results.

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The problem of equal rights of men and women has been in the center of people's attention since the beginning of time. However, the ancient Greek scientist Pythagoras was the thinker who recognized that women have equal rights with men. The Greek scientist Pythagoras developed ideas that people's lives should be reformed and harmonized with the conclusions of philosophy about rights and freedom. From this point of view, he expanded the ideas about the equal creation of men and women.

By the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the issues of the role and participation of women in the social and political life of the society were in the focus of Turkestan enlighteners. Abdurauf Fitrat, one of the representatives of Jadidism, the main part of his work on "Family" is dedicated to women, how to respect her and how to treat her. In the play "Should girls study?" there is a sentence. According to the author, a person's intellectual condition and education largely depend on women and mothers. According to the work, a man is busy earning food and drink for a living, and a woman must be more educated than a man, because she is mainly involved with children. Therefore, it is important for women to be enlightened as the educators of the nation. In this regard, on International Women's Day, March 8, 2021, UNICEF called on women and girls to ensure gender equality and focused on expanding their opportunities to build a better future. This requires active participation of women in the economic, political and social spheres, expanding access to formal and informal education, investing in girls' participation in science, technology, engineering and mathematics and acquisition of digital skills. Gender equality is not only a basic human right, but also an important foundation for achieving peace, prosperity and sustainable development around the world.

At the new stage of Uzbekistan's development, under the leadership of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, 2 laws, 2 decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 6 decisions and 4 orders of the Government were adopted on the comprehensive support of women in the country. A committee on issues of women and girls and gender equality was established in the Senate of the Oliy

Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This structure plays an important role in increasing the socio-political activity of women in the society and creating wide opportunities for them. The adopted laws state that increasing the socio-political activity of women in our country, ensuring gender equality, expanding the rights and opportunities of all women, and creating favorable conditions for the realization of abilities and opportunities in various fields is an important priority of state policy. provides. In the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan mentions the equality of men and women (Article 58), protection of motherhood and childhood, free and equal marriage (Article 76), responsibility of parents to raise and raise children (Article 77 article) rules are defined. As President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Today, as a result of our large-scale democratic reforms, the participation of our women in political and social processes is increasing. Of the 150 deputies elected to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 48 or 32 percent were women. This figure has exceeded 25 percent in the Senate and local councils. It should be noted that for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the National Parliament reached a level consistent with the recommendations set by the UN. The parliament of our country has risen to the 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in terms of the number of female deputies. However, please note that 5 years ago we were in 128th place. About 28,000 of our sisters are provided with practical assistance in entrepreneurship, crafts, vocational retraining, and employment. Also, within the framework of five important initiatives, 21,500 of our girls were trained in short-term vocational courses.

In our country, efforts to ensure gender equality and increase the role of women in social and political life are being carried out in several directions:

- improvement of legislation on women's rights;
- improvement of the institutional foundations of women's protection;
- increase the awareness of the population about gender equality and women's rights;

- training of responsible officials on the basis of relevant legal norms to ensure their compliance in the practice of law enforcement.

As a practical expression of strengthening the role of women and girls in the field of state and society building and increasing their political rights, women are called "Hero of Uzbekistan", "Deputy", "Senator", "Minister", "Deputy Minister", "Academic", " Adding terms such as "Scientist", "Entrepreneur", "Director" is a clear example of this. In conclusion, it can be said that the equal

rights of men and women play an important role in the well-being of the people, social peace and economic stability.

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